

Enhancing Competitiveness, Resilience and Sustainability of Remote Farming, Forestry and Rural Areas through Holistic Assessment of Smart XG, Last-mile and Edge Solutions' Gains

D4.1: Techno-economic assessment of last-mile and edge technological solutions (1st version)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	Fifth Generation
A/C	Air Condition
API	Application Programming Interface
BEREC	Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications
BRAS	Broadband Remote Access Server
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CEX	Central Exchange
CO	Central Office
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment
DB	Database
DCF	Discounted Cash Flow
DEMUX	Demultiplexer
DNS	Domain Name Server
EC	European Commission
EECC	European Electronic Communications Code
FP	Flexibility Point
FTTC	Fibre to the Curb
FTTH	Fibre to the Home
GE	Gigabit Ethernet
GPON	Gigabit Passive Optical Network
HTTP	Hyper-Text Transfer Protocol
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IRR	Internal Rate of Return

KFT	Knowledge Facilitation Tool
LEX	Local Exchange
LL	Links Level
MTBF	Mean Time Between Failures
MTTR	Mean Time to Repair
MUX	Multiplexer
NFS	Network File System
NGN	Next Generation Networks
NMS	Network Management System
NPV	Net Present Value
OA&M	Operation, Administration and Maintenance
OLT	Optical Line Termination
ONT	Optical Network Termination
ONU	Optical Network Unit
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
PON	Passive Optical Network
PSU	Power Supply Unit
REST	Representational State Transfer
TE	Techno-economic
VAS	Value Added Services
VDSL	Very High-Speed Digital Subscriber Line
VHC	Very High-Capacity

1 Executive Summary

The XGain project aims to promote sustainable and inclusive development in rural, coastal, and sub-urban areas by providing access to a comprehensive inventory of smart XG, last-mile connectivity, and edge computing solutions for relevant stakeholders such as municipalities, policymakers, farmers, foresters and their associations. The project's overall objective is to deliver a Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT) to aid in business model development and decision-making in selecting technology ecosystems that increase systemic resilience and energy efficiency, contribute to climate mitigation, and reduce digital divides among different groups.

The purpose of this report is dual (a) to provide a methodology for the techno-economic (TE) assessment of the required Information and Communication Technology (ICT) investments including connectivity, edge processing, hardware and software solutions and (b) to describe the approach towards a platform that allows applying the methodology on specific case studies.

Towards the first purpose, the inputs and outputs of the methodology are provided and the components of the techno-economic model are described in detail. A geometric model for the calculation of ducts and fibre lengths is also provided. Dimensioning rules for Fibre to the Curb Very High-Speed Digital Subscriber Line (FTTC-VDSL) and Fibre to the Home - xPassive Optical Network (FTTH-xPON) networks are defined enabling the calculation of the required number of equipment components per technology. All these TE components will be implemented as modules of the techno-economic tool which will be part of KFT. The software development methodology of these modules is also provided.

Towards the second purpose, a methodology and strategy for the delivery of a TE Analysis Framework is presented. It follows the Agile methodology, and the strategic goal is to present a solution that on the one hand covers the needs of the analysis methodology but is also capable to adapt to further analysis needs, and on the other hand can be delivered as a modern, cross platform, scalable, cloud-based service. Certain boundaries to the design are set, in order to arrive to tangible results within a specific timeframe, however the flexibility of the platform allows those barriers to be lifted with additive changes, if required.

At the time of this first report the implementation is tackling specific calculations, while in the second stage and until the next, last, update, these will be integrated, benchmarked and evaluated, and the results will be presented in the update of the report on month 25 of the project.

2 Introduction

Citizens expect a fast and reliable internet connection whether they are at work, at home, or on the move. A high-quality, fast, and secure internet is essential for modern societies and economies to thrive in the future. Investments in high-capacity networks are increasingly important in various sectors such as education, healthcare, manufacturing, transportation etc.

To encourage both private and public investments in fast and ultra-fast networks and enable individuals and businesses to fully benefit from digitalisation, the European Commission (EC) has implemented policy measures and financial instruments. The initial broadband provision objectives [1] were:

- Basic broadband for all citizens by 2013. This target has been met, as satellite broadband is available in all Member States and has a 100% coverage;
- Coverage of Next Generation Networks (NGN): 30 Mbps or more for all citizens by 2020. Not met by all Member States by 2020;
- Use of NGN: 100 Mbps or more for 50% of households by 2020. Not met by all Member States by 2020.

In September 2016, the EC introduced the "Connectivity for a Competitive Digital Single Market - Towards a European Gigabit Society" strategy. This strategy focuses on enhancing the availability and adoption of high-capacity networks to facilitate widespread use of new digital products, services, and applications in the Digital Single Market.

In line with these efforts, the EC has set a second set of strategic objectives and connectivity targets for 2025 [2]:

- Access to at least 1 Gbps for all schools, transport hubs, and main providers of public services and digitally intensive enterprises;
- Access to download speeds of at least 100 Mbps to be upgraded to 1 Gbps for all European households;
- Uninterrupted 5G wireless broadband coverage for all urban areas and major roads and railways.

In addition, the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) [3] and the Agency for Support of the Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications (BEREC) [4] were established in December 2018. These are vital for achieving connectivity targets and enhancing Europe's competitiveness. They facilitate the deployment of high-capacity networks across the EU, protect digital rights of citizens, and provide incentives for investors and operators to make necessary investments.

Additionally, the EC has implemented regulations to decrease the expenses associated with deploying high-speed broadband. The cost of civil engineering works, which can vary depending on the terrain, can account for up to 80% of the total cost of deploying high-speed broadband networks. By minimising these costs, the roll-out of broadband can become more cost-effective.

The Directive on measures to reduce the cost of deploying high-speed electronic communications networks (2014/61/EU) [5] and the EECC have been introduced to facilitate and incentivise the deployment of high-speed electronic communications networks by reducing expenses. These measures primarily focus on four areas:

- Access of operators willing to deploy high-speed broadband networks to existing physical infrastructure (e.g., ducts, poles, masts), including that for electricity transmission/distribution and other utilities;

- Efficient coordination of civil works;
- Faster, simpler and more transparent permit-granting procedures;
- Equipment of new buildings and major renovations with high-speed physical infrastructures (e.g., miniducts, access points) and access to in-building infrastructure.

Although all these measures have significantly improved the coverage of high-capacity networks, there are still variations between countries and rural areas. Remote and rural regions do have less access to high-speed broadband due to infrastructure challenges and the high cost of deployment. Rural communities are facing slower internet connections or relying on alternative technologies such as satellite or fixed wireless access, which may not offer the speeds required for advanced applications.

Many governments around the world have launched initiatives and funding programs to promote the deployment of high-capacity networks in rural areas. These programs aim to incentivise private sector investment, support community broadband projects, and subsidise internet access for underserved areas. Collaboration between governments and private entities is crucial in expanding broadband access in rural areas. Public-private partnerships leverage the resources and expertise of both sectors to improve infrastructure deployment, reduce costs, and increase the reach of high-capacity networks. However, it is of paramount importance to have a tool able to assess the required investments in these areas. As a first step, in this deliverable, a techno-economic methodology for the assessment of the necessary investments is provided.

2.1 Mapping XGain Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map XGain Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to XGain GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

XGain GA Component Title	XGain GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D4.1 Techno-economic assessment of last-mile and edge technological solutions			
Initial (A) version overviewing existing methods.			
TASKS			
T4.1 Techno-economic Assessment of Last-mile and Edge	Task 4.1 will be responsible for the techno-economic assessment of all available last mile solutions at farm, community, and regional level. It will further develop the existing	All Chapters	In this initial version of deliverable D4.1, the techno-economic methodology that will be implemented for the assessment of potential investments is described.

<p>Technological Solutions</p>	<p>methodology by including dimensioning rules for all the technological solutions that will be examined in the Use Cases. The results will be in the form of economic indicators such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and payback period for the examined solutions. It will take as input the requirements of the stakeholders, the characteristics of the area (at farm community and regional level), the service requirements, network architectures, demand forecast and produce a detailed list of required network components over the study period. By combining this list with the cost of network components and the expected price evolution.</p> <p>It will calculate the economic indicators that will be used for the assessment of the different scenarios.</p>		<p>The final version of the deliverable (D4.2) will provide the findings and derived results from the assessment of the different scenarios.</p>
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2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The current deliverable is presenting the first outcomes of T4.1 Techno-economic Assessment of Last-mile and Edge Technological Solutions. This deliverable serves as an initial report of D4.1 and will be complemented and enhanced by a second deliverable D4.2 (version 2), which will illustrate the results from the implementation of the techno-economic methodology on the different scenarios.

More specifically, the document is divided logically into three main sections:

- Techno-economic methodology (sections 3 & 4)
- Dimensioning rules of fixed networks (section 5)
- Implementation methodology of the different modules (section 6)

It should be stressed that the techno-economic methodology/framework described in this deliverable is a significant part of the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT) allowing the estimation of deployment and operation cost of connectivity, edge solutions and/or enablers in case of individual users as well as the extra functionality to calculate potential revenues in case of communities, regions or network providers. The techno-economic tool mainly receives input from WP3 and provides outputs to Task 4.4.

3 Techno-economic Methodology

In this section, the methodology that will be used in order to assess the business cases under investigation is described. The techno-economic methodology used for the assessment of the cases has already been adopted in numerous similar studies [6]. The initial techno-economic methodology has been improved by including edge computing solutions. The framework of the XGain techno-economic evaluations is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Framework of XGain Techno-economic Evaluation

The core part of the techno-economic model is in a **DataBase (DB)**, which will be regularly updated with data (e.g., network components) collected from the largest European telecommunication companies and vendors as well as from benchmarks from the telecom market [6][7].

The study period is always adapted to the case under investigation. For the case of a network deployment and considering the time a network -or a service- needs to reach market maturity to pay back investments, an eight to ten-year period appears as reasonable. The list of provided **services** is defined and their market penetration (**Demand**) over the study period is calculated. Moreover, econometric and price forecast models are used to define **service tariffs**. By combining market penetration and tariff evolution, one can calculate the received **revenues** for each service.

Next, the **architecture** scenarios to provide the selected service set must be defined. This needs detailed network planning expertise and specialized software which is mostly outside the scope of the framework of XGain methodology. Thus, it was decided to perform the dimensioning using assumptions and rules. For fixed networks, the tool includes a **geometric model** that will assist in the network planning by automatically calculating lengths

for cables and ducts. These geometric models are optional parts of the methodology and the KFT can be used without them, e.g., for radio access technology evaluation, where no geometric models are necessary. The result of the architecture scenario definition is the so-called shopping list. This list is made for each year of the study period, and it shows the volumes of all network cost elements (equipment, cables, cabinets, ducting, installation etc.) and the distribution of these network components over different flexibility points and link levels. A price evolution is calculated for all network components by using the extended learning curve model [8]. CAPEX (Capital Expenditure)/**investments** is then calculated by combining the required number of components and their price for each year.

Operation, Administration and Maintenance (OA&M) expenditures are also calculated in the techno-economic tool. For example, energy costs are evaluated, based on the power consumption of components and the average cost of one kWh [9]. Maintenance costs are also estimated. They consist of two parts: (i) the cost of repair, calculated as a fixed percentage of the total investments in network elements, and; (ii) the cost of repair work, that has been calculated based on the Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) and the Mean Time To Repair (MTTR).

By combining service revenues, investments, operating costs and general economic inputs (e.g., discount rate, tax rate) the tool calculates the **results** necessary for Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) analysis such as cash flows, Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), payback period and other economic figures of merit.

More details on the methodology and the outputs are presented in the following paragraphs.

3.1 Key Model Inputs

The main inputs for the model evaluations are the network architecture and service scenarios. The subscriber density is the most important parameter to the geometric model.

3.1.1 Network Architecture Scenario

The architecture scenario is defined in a shopping list which indicates how the network is rolled out during the study period. The shopping list defines the amount of equipment needed in the network as a function of time.

3.1.2 Service Scenario

The service scenario defines how many subscribers are connected to a certain service at a certain moment and how much revenue one user means for the network operator per year. The penetration of the service, expressed in terms of the number of users subscribing to the service versus time, is a key input to the model.

3.1.3 Subscriber Density

The methodology supports the use of a geometric model to calculate cable and duct lengths in the fixed network. The main input to the geometric model is the subscribers' density. This parameter is often used to study the sensitivity of the cost of the system to various geographic conditions.

3.2 Key Model Outputs

Depending on the complexity of the scenario, various commonly used indicators like Payback Period, NPV or IRR, can give different results in comparisons. In addition, it is often necessary to use several figures of merit for the studies to get a thorough understanding of the economics for each scenario. In some cases, it is also advisable to apply sensitivity analysis and/or risk assessment methodologies to the less accurate inputs using multiple figures of merit as indicators.

3.2.1 Investments

Since the methodology studies scenarios, investments are usually spread over the study period. To get a single figure of merit for the total investment, the future investments are discounted to the beginning of the study period using the conventional discounting formula. The total discounted investment cost is usually called First Installed Cost.

In the methodology the network is subdivided into a hierarchy of flexibility points and link levels (see Geometric Modelling, further in this document). Links interconnect flexibility points. All links or flexibility points in the same hierarchical level form a so-called network level. The current implementation of the methodology allows the investments to be analysed based on physical location of the cost components in the network (by hierarchical network level).

3.2.2 Revenues

Regarding the revenues, the methodology is simply using a service connection tariff and estimating a certain annual tariff for each service per connected customer. In general, both connection tariffs and usage tariffs are time series over the study period.

3.2.3 Life Cycle Cost

Life Cycle Cost is defined as the sum of global discounted investments and global discounted running (or OA&M) costs. This value represents the total cost for constructing and running the network over the study period.

Often the sole reason for a techno-economic study is the evaluation of the cost of the proposed network build. The reason might be a new network or an upgrade of an existing one. In these cases, it is not always necessary to add any service revenues to the study and the final result of the study can be either First Installed Cost or Life Cycle Cost of the project. Thus, this methodology and as a consequence the tool are especially suitable for comparative studies between competing network technologies. In case of already existing network, this tool can be used for the calculation of the cost of deployment and operation of enablers as well as for cost-based pricing purposes.

3.2.4 Cash Balance

The Cash Balance or Cumulative Cash Flow time-series is a very informative figure for a specific network/ service scenario. Especially for a green field case³ it gives much information in a single picture.

A typical Cash Balance curve for a network scenario goes first deeply down to the negative side because of the high initial investments. If the scenario is profitable, the cash flow turns positive fairly soon and the Cash Balance curve starts to rise. The lowest point in the Cash Balance curve gives the amount of funding required for the project. The point in time when the Cash Balance turns positive gives the Payback Period for the project.

In an investment scenario where most of the expenditure happens at the beginning of the study period, the Payback Period gives a good indication of the efficiency of the investment. If the scenario is more complex, that is, if there are for example several upgrades, it is not possible to define a single Payback Period. It is still possible to use the Cash Balance curve as an indicator for the profitability of the scenario. In this case, it is important to study the trend of cash flow at the end of the study period.

3.2.5 Net Present Value

The Net Present Value gives a single figure of merit for a project. Its definition is the Sum of Discounted Cash Flows plus the Discounted Rest Value of the project. It is a good indicator for the profitability of the scenario especially in the cases where the Payback Period cannot be used because major investments are spread out in time.

The weakest point in this figure of merit is the definition or calculation of the rest value of the network. There are several ways to try to define this value. The usual approach uses the bookkeeping value of the network as the Rest Value because it is the only figure that can be calculated from the inputs already available.

3.2.6 Internal Rate of Return

IRR is the discount rate at which the NPV is zero. If the IRR is higher than the opportunity cost of money (that is, interest of an average long-term investment), the project is viable.

If the scenarios to be compared are not similar, for example if the size of the networks is different, these cannot be easily compared using Net Present Values. In these cases, Internal Rate of Return gives a good indication on how good “value for money” these projects have.

It should be highlighted that in case of an individual user, the outcomes are limited to investments as well as OA&M expenses.

3.3 Improvements

After the first run and the analysis of the extracted results, several improvements would be performed by taking also into account late feedback from the stakeholders.

³ A green field case is a case that is built from scratch that is the installation and configuration of the network are entirely new.

Towards this direction, sensitivity and risk analyses are useful tools.

3.3.1 Sensitivity Analysis

The derived results concern a set of scenarios with specific parameters values. However, in case of critical parameters values fluctuations, sensitivity analysis should be performed. The parameters are modified by a selected percentage (%) in order to assess their impact on the key performance indicators of the project. Note that sensitivity analysis can be performed for all parameters that affect both the model and the key financial indicators.

3.3.2 Risk and Opportunity Analysis

The consortium will also investigate the inclusion of a risk and opportunity analysis to the tool. The risk methodology is based on the use of simulation and more precisely Monte Carlo simulation⁴. The underlying variables in a business case (e.g.: prices, future market shares, cost evolution and demand) are inherently uncertain. This means, that the decision maker must model the uncertainty of relevant variables, in order to “check” the impact on the derived results. Uncertainty about a situation can often indicate risk, which is the possibility of loss, damage or any other undesirable event.

The difference between traditional “plain” sensitivity analysis and risk analysis based on Monte Carlo simulation is that the former only informs someone about what is possible; not about what is probable! In traditional sensitivity analysis, a number of variables are selected for the study and varied one at a time, to see the impact on the main result. Often what-if scenarios are constructed with different combinations of worst-case, moderate and best-case values of each of the variables – which becomes a very time-consuming process.

Monte Carlo simulation, however, makes possible not only to assign probabilities to each variable (knowing that some variables are more uncertain than others) but also to update all the selected variables automatically and simultaneously. Random numbers are generated for each of the selected variables for the risk analysis by selecting specific probability distribution functions.

The simulation, therefore, calculates a large number of what-if scenarios. Furthermore, the simulation keeps track of the calculations by measuring the impact on the result from the changes in each of the variables.

The type of distribution to choose for the variables under investigation is based on its conditions. For instance, it can be a variable that can never be outside a given interval, e.g., never being negative.

After having run a simulation of, for example, 1000 trials, 1000 possible outcomes have been created compared to the single value obtained in the deterministic model. In addition to the statistics (mean value, percentiles and standard deviation) on the result variable(s), the input variables are ranked with respect to their impact on the outputs. The measure is either the contribution to the variance of the output variable(s) or the rank correlation. Some variables may show very little significance after all and could therefore be removed in future simulations. This will increase clarity as well as reduce the time it takes to complete a simulation.

⁴ For further details see, for example: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/montecarlosimulation.asp>

Most often, probability distributions are defined by a mean value and a standard deviation. However, these parameters are not very intuitive. It is more intuitive to describe a variable by a default value/most expected value and by a confidence interval. A confidence interval of 90% means that there is a probability of 90% that the variable will take a value within the specified interval in a trial of a simulation.

4 Components of the Techno-economic Model

4.1 System Dimensioning

The aim of system dimensioning is the estimation of the required number of resources such as HW and SW components. The dimensioning process may begin by estimating the use of sub-components required in order to satisfy the technical requirements and provide the necessary services.

The main parameters that are used in system dimensioning can be divided into two categories:

- Technical parameters.
- Market related parameters (forecasted demand).

Since the results of system dimensioning will significantly affect the reliability and the initial cost of deployment, each parameter used in the dimensioning process should be examined in depth. It should be highlighted that the dimensioning rules of the wireless solutions are described in the deliverable D3.1, while the rules of the fixed networks are provided in Section 5.

4.2 Demand Modelling

As shown in the previous section, services demand significantly influences system dimensioning and, as a consequence, both the system/infrastructure and services cost. An overview of the forecasting methodology adopted for the needs of this work is presented. The most common approach for estimating and forecasting the new product's sales are mainly based on **the use of innovation diffusion models**.

One of the main central themes of the innovation field is the mathematical modelling of innovation diffusion, for different types of innovations and under different assumptions. The main finding can be summarised to a bell-shaped curve depicting the frequency of adoption against time and an S-shaped curve, when the cumulative number of adopters is plotted. During the first stages of the innovation life cycle (the introduction stage), the adoption rate is relatively low, followed by the next stage (the take off), described by a high rate of adoption, until the peak of the bell curve is reached, which corresponds to the inflection point of the cumulative adoption. After that time adoption rate decreases again, until the market saturation level is asymptotically met, and the maximum number of adopters is reached. This corresponds to the end of the life cycle of the innovation, which in the cases of high technology products, is usually replaced by its descendant generation. The above concepts are graphically illustrated in Figure 2, where the first plot depicts adoptions per time period and the second the corresponding cumulative adoptions.

Figure 2: Idealised Diffusion Process of an Innovation, a: Adoption per Time Period (Bell curve), b: Cumulative Penetration of Adoption (S-Curve)

The most well-known diffusion models that are widely used for technology demand estimation and forecasting are the Bass model [10], the Fisher – Pry model [11], the logistic family models [12] and the Gompertz model [13]. All of these models are capable of providing an S- shaped curve describing the technology diffusion among specific populations. These models can provide demand forecasting at the aggregate (population) level, rather than at the individual customer level. The latter approach can be described by “choice-based” models, which mainly focus on estimating and quantifying individuals’ probability to adopt the innovation, taking into account customer preferences and technology determinants/ characteristics.

The logistic and the Gompertz model, which are used into the context of the present work, are constructed based on a differential equation of the following form:

$$\frac{dY(t)}{dt} = (a + bY(t))f(S - Y(t)) \quad (1)$$

where $Y(t)$ represents cumulative penetration at time t , S is the saturation level of the specific technology and a , b are the parameters of innovation and imitation respectively. Finally, f , is a function of the remaining market potential $S - Y(t)$. As observed in (1), the diffusion speed is proportionate to both the population that has already adopted the service, denoted by $Y(t)$, and the remaining market potential, represented by $S - Y(t)$, through the corresponding transformation function f .

Concerning the logistic model its mathematical formulation is given by:

$$\frac{dY(t)}{dt} = (a + bY(t))(S - Y(t)) \quad (2)$$

and the Gompertz model by:

$$\frac{dY(t)}{dt} = rY(t)\ln(S/Y(t)) \quad (3)$$

In many cases, the diffusion process is considered as only an imitation process, therefore the corresponding coefficient of innovation (the parameter a in (1) and (2)) is set to zero. The solution of the above differential equations yields the general formulations of the models. More specifically, the linear logistic model formulation (also known as the Fisher-Pry model) is given by:

$$Y(t) = \frac{S}{1+e^{-a-bt}} \quad (4)$$

and the Gompertz by:

$$Y(t) = Se^{ae^{-rt}} \quad (5)$$

Apart from the above model descriptions, corresponding formulations exist which incorporate the initial values of diffusion, recorded at the beginning of the process. More specifically, if at time $t=t_0$ (usually $t_0=0$) the corresponding recorded value was $Y(t_0)=Y_0$, then the formulations provided by (4) and (5), respectively, become:

$$Y(t) = \frac{S}{1+\left(\frac{S}{Y_0}-1\right)e^{-a-b(t-t_0)}} \quad (6)$$

and:

$$Y(t) = S \left(\frac{Y_0}{S}\right)^{e^{-bt}} \quad (7)$$

4.3 Cost Evolution of Components

Components' cost is following the ICT market evolution with respect to substantial learning curves. For each component cost prediction, a price curve (learning curve) is calculated representing the component's cost throughout the study period. In fact, the price $P(t)$ of each network element is assumed to follow the extended learning curve [14].

$$P(t) = P(0) \left[n_r(0)^{-1} \left\{ 1 + e^{\ln[n_r(0)^{-1}-1] - \frac{2\ln 9}{\Delta T} t} \right\}^{-1} \right]^{\log_2 K} \quad (8)$$

where $P(0)$ is the price of the component in the reference year 0, $n_r(0)$ is referring to the units of the component that were sold in the reference year 0, ΔT is the time that is needed for the total production to grow from 10 % to 90 % of the maximum value and K is a learning curve coefficient that actually points to the price reduction that happens when the production volume is doubled. In cases where historical data are available, the parameters K and ΔT can be determined using a standard regression analysis. The components and subsystems are grouped in several volume classes. In the same way the K parameter is estimated based on type of component or subsystem, reflecting the learning process from other similar components or systems.

In addition, the volume classes are chosen to cover the two aspects of cost components: the type and maturity of cost components. The definition Old, Mature, etc. stands for the years during which the specific components were offered in the market. The definition Fast, Medium, etc. stands for time in years to grow the total production volume from 10% to 90% of its maximum value.

4.4 OA&M Methodology

OA&M approach in the methodology states that OA&M costs are divided into three separate components. Conceptually the three components are defined as follows:

- **M₁** - Represents the cost of repair parts. This component is included automatically in the model and is proportional to the cumulative investments in the network.
- **M₂** - Represents the cost of repair work. This is also automatically included in the model and is calculated as:

$$M_2 = P_1 \frac{MTTR}{MTBR} \tag{9}$$

with,

P_1 , the cost of labour, defined as a time series over the study period,

MTBR, the Mean Time Between Repairs, included in the database per component,

MTTR, the Mean Time To Repair, included in the database per component

- **O&A** - This component represents Operation & Administration costs, and it has to be included manually when building models. Typically, it would be driven by services, e.g., by number of customers, or by number of critical network elements.

Figure 3: The OA&M Methodology

The total maintenance cost caused by a single cost component in year i is:

$$M_i = (M_1 + M_2)_i = \frac{V_{i-1} + V_i}{2} \left(P_i R_{class} + P_1 \frac{MTTR}{MTBR} \right) \quad (10)$$

where,

V_i is the equipment volume in year i

P_i is the price of cost item in year i

R_{class} is the maintenance cost percentage (defined by choosing Maintenance Material Class for every cost component)

P_1 is the cost of one working hour

$MTTR$ is the mean time to repair for the cost item in question

$MTBR$ is the mean time between failures for the cost item in question

4.5 Geometric Modelling for Telecom Networks

4.5.1 Introduction

The cost of digging trenches, installing ducts and cables is crucial in the economics of any telecommunications network infrastructure. A geometric model is used to estimate the amount of cable, ducts and civil works (trenches) required in such network. On a conceptual level the geometric model is a function that takes several inputs such as subscriber density, network topology (star, ring, bus), average over-length (adjustment of model outputs), duct availability, etc. and outputs values like trench length, duct length and cable length. As the geometric model delivers the basis for the quantity calculation of some very important cost components, it is an important and fundamental step towards the broader task of techno-economic modelling of a telecommunications project. Various geometric models were developed and used in the past. The model that will be used in the KFT is described below.

4.5.2 The Geometric Model

The basic structure of the model is based on a star topology and a polygon geometry. In many cases this is a valid assumption, but there are cases where the polygon structure is not ideal. In a more advanced version, the model allows modelling of clustered areas where subscribers are not homogeneously distributed. The topology can be also a star, ring or bus or a combination of them. In addition, the shape of the model area and location of flexibility points within the model area are taken into consideration.

Figure 4: First Three Levels of the Geometric Model

In Figure 4, the basic structure of the geometric model is shown. The model is based on a layered structure in which each layer uses the same basic geometric model, but with different parameters. A model layer represents a specific type of Flexibility Point (FP), and is characterised by the FP area density and distribution ratio. The distribution ratio n at a given layer or network level represents the number of lower-level flexibility points linked to this flexibility point (e.g., 50 optical nodes linked to 1 aggregation node). Link Levels (LL) interconnect the flexibility points of different levels (e.g., LL2 interconnects FP1 and FP2).

Total trench, duct and cable lengths in the model area are achieved by simply adding lengths from different layers. Between the layers there can be a certain amount of empty space. One layer can, for example, represent a village and next higher layer will be a larger region where there are scattered villages and uninhabited areas in between.

The basic model area in each layer is rectangular as depicted in Figure 5. The area has a length of “a” units and a width of “b” units. The unit value relates to the density of flexibility points in the model layer area. For a homogeneous distribution of flexibility points with a density d_f , a unit is $1/\text{SQRT}(d_f)$. On the lowest level of the network model, where the Flexibility Point (FPO) usually refers to the subscriber location, d_f equals the subscriber density d_s in the considered area. The higher-level flexibility point densities are calculated from d_s by considering specific dimensioning rules (e.g., maximum optical node size will define the optical node density as a function of the subscriber density). Further in this section we will look at the normalised case with unit value set to 1.

Figure 5: Basic Model Area for One Model Layer

4.5.2.1 Star type topology

Figure 6 shows how the ducts are located within the basic model area in case of a star type link level topology. As an example a connection (cable route) between the flexibility point (x,y) and the lower level flexibility point (i,j) is shown.

Figure 6: Basic Model Area for a Star Topology

The duct length l_d is equal to the trench length and given by

$$l_d = ab - 1 = n - 1 \quad (11)$$

where n is the distribution ratio at given network level. Each square in the model area represents a lower model layer or at the lowest level a subscriber. The sublayer/subscriber located at point (i,j) will be connected to distribution point (x,y) with a cable that makes one rectangular turn on its way. The total cable length will be:

$$l_c(a, b, x, y) = \sum_{i=0}^{b-1} \sum_{j=0}^{a-1} [|i - y| + |j - x|] \quad (12)$$

where:

a is the length of the model area

b is the width of the model area and

x is the length co-ordinate of distribution point, $x \in [0, a - 1]$ and

y is the width co-ordinate of distribution point, $y \in [0, \beta - 1]$

After some manipulation this yields to:

$$l_c(a, b, x, y) = \frac{a}{2} [(b - y - 1)^2 + y^2 + b - 1] + \frac{b}{2} [(a - x - 1)^2 + x^2 + a - 1] \quad (13)$$

The variables used in equation (13) are not very suitable for use in the final application. It is more intuitive to express the cable length as a function of distribution ratio n , area shape s and position of distribution point p . The shape factor s indicates the shape of the model area, i.e., if the area is a square or rectangle ($a=sb$). The position variable $p \in [0,1]$ equals zero when the distribution point is in the middle of the area. As p grows the distribution point moves along the arrow in Figure 5 towards the corner of the area. When p is equal to one, the distribution point is in the corner of the area.

Now a , b , x and y can be expressed as a function of n , s and p as follows:

$$a = \sqrt{ns} \quad (14a)$$

$$b = \sqrt{\frac{n}{s}} \quad (14b)$$

$$x = \frac{\sqrt{ns}-1}{2}(1-p) \quad (14c)$$

$$y = \frac{\sqrt{n/s}-1}{2}(1-p) \quad (14d)$$

Substituting these into (13) the cable length is given as a function of n , s and p .

4.5.2.2 Bus Type Topology

Figure 7 shows how the trenches, ducts and cables are located within the basic model area in case of a bus type link level topology. The calculation of lengths is rather simple in this case.

Figure 7: Basic Model Area for a Bus Topology ($n=45$)

Duct or trench length l_d and cable length l_c can be expressed as:

$$l_d = n - 1 \quad (15a)$$

$$l_c = n - 1 \quad (15b)$$

4.5.2.3 Ring type topology

Figure 8 shows how the trenches, ducts and cables are located within the basic model area in case of a ring type link level topology. The calculation of lengths is also rather simple in this case.

Figure 8: Basic Model Area for a Ring Topology (n=54)

Duct or trench length l_d and cable length l_c can be expressed as:

$$l_d = n \quad (16a)$$

$$l_c = n \quad (16b)$$

5 Dimensioning of Fixed Networks

5.1 Fibre to the Curb – VDSL network

A fibre to the curb – VDSL network is modeled (Figure 9). The network can be divided in four levels according to the type of node that is hosted in each level. More specifically, each of these four levels contain respectively the necessary amount of the following elements:

- customer premises equipment (CPE)
- Cabinet
- Local Exchange (LEX)
- Central Exchange (CEX)/Central Office (CO)

The number of users and the required nodes (cabinets, LEX and CEX) are considered uniformly distributed in the area under investigation.

A geometric model is used in order to calculate the required distances for both duct and fibre routes between LEX – cabinets and CEX- LEX considering a star topology.

Figure 9: FTTC – VDSL Architecture Under Investigation

Figure 10-Figure 12 are magnified versions of each node describing the equipment – components that are incorporated therein.

Figure 10: FTTC-VDSL Cabinet Description

Figure 11: FTTC-VDSL LEX Description

Figure 12: FTTC-VDSL CEX Description

From the bottom (customer premises) to the top (CEX), the model is as follows. The number of the CPEs is equal to the total number of customers. In the next level, the number of cabinets is estimated in order to satisfy both the coverage and the capacity requirements:

$$\# \text{ of cabinets} = \max \left[\frac{\text{area}}{\text{Cabinets_max_coverage_area}}, \frac{\# \text{ of customers}}{\text{Cabinets max user capacity}} \right] \quad (17)$$

The necessary number of VDSL cards that are included in the cabinet is calculated based on the number of customers and the number of ports per VDSL card.

In the next two levels, the number of LEX is calculated from the required number of cabinets and the maximum number of cabinets per LEX while only one CEX (located in the centre of the area) is assumed to serve the area under investigation.

In order to estimate the required number of ports facing both the lower and the upper levels, the traffic in each node is calculated. The total traffic generated by the customers of the network is equal to the product of the respective customers by the respective bit rate. In order to calculate the traffic per node per level, one should divide the total traffic by the number of level's nodes, respectively.

In this model, two types of Gigabit Ethernet (GE) ports (1GE and 10GE) are used in both the backplane of the cabinets and the backplane/frontplane of the LEX and CEX. The required number of 1GE and 10GE ports in the backplane of each node is evaluated through equations (18a) and (18b) respectively.

$$\# \text{ of 1GE ports} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\text{Node's traffic (Mbps)}}{\text{Node's Contention Ratio} \times 1000} \right) \quad (18a)$$

$$\# \text{ of 10GE ports} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\text{Node's traffic (Mbps)}}{\text{Node's Contention Ratio} \times 10000} \right) \quad (18b)$$

The decision between multiple 1GEports or one 10GE port is based on a threshold (parameter) about the maximum number of 1GE ports, after this threshold is reached instead of multiple 1GE ports the solution of 10GE port is selected. The number of required ports in the frontplane is straightforward and is equal to the number of the backplane ports of the lower level's node. Thus, the total number of ports in each node corresponds to the sum of the frontplane and the backplane ports.

In the next step, one should calculate the required number of 1GE and 10GE cards (19) as well as the required chassis (20) per node. Both are limited by the maximum number of ports per card and the maximum number of slots (for cards) per chassis respectively.

$$\# \text{ of } 1GE \text{ cards} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\text{Node's } 1GE \text{ (10GE) ports}}{\# \text{ of ports per } 1GE \text{ (10GE) card}} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$\# \text{ of chassis} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\text{Node's } 1GE \text{ cards} + \text{Node's } 10GE \text{ cards}}{\# \text{ of slots per chassis}} \right) \quad (20)$$

The total number of 1GE (10GE) ports and cards as well as the total number of chassis in each level are estimated by multiplying the respective values per node with the number of nodes in each level. It should also be noted that the number of Air Condition (A/C) and Power Supply Units (PSUs) in each level equal to the total number of nodes (cabinets, LEX and CEX) in each level.

Finally, there are two sets of components whose required number is calculated using equations (21) and (22). The first set which consists of Broadband Remote Access Server (BRAS), call server, call server software and Remote Authentication Dial-In User Service (RADIUS) uses the number of simultaneous connected users in the network as a driver:

$$\# \text{ of} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\text{Total customers} \times \text{Max_simultaneous_connected_users}}{\text{Component's capacity}} \right) \quad (21)$$

while the second (billing, Intelligent Network Value Added Services (IN/VAS) and Network Management System (NMS)) uses the total number of customers as a driver:

$$\# \text{ of} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\text{Total customers}}{\text{Component's capacity}} \right) \quad (22)$$

The required number of Domain Name Servers (DNS) is assumed to be equal to the number of CEX.

5.2 Fibre to the Home – xPON network

A fibre to the home – Gigabit Passive Optical Network (GPON) is modelled (Figure 13). The network can be divided in four levels according to the type of node that is hosted in each level. More specifically, each of these four levels contain respectively the necessary amount of the following elements:

- CPE and Optical Network Unit ONU/Optical Network Termination (ONT)
- Building optical splitter
- Cabinet / Optical Mux/Demux
- Central Office (CO)/OLT

The number of users and the required nodes are again considered uniformly distributed in the area under investigation.

A geometric model is used in order to calculate the required distances for both duct and fibre routes between CO – cabinets, cabinets – ONUs considering a star topology. It should be highlighted that the maximum distance from the CO to the customers cannot be greater than 15km.

Figure 13: FTTH – GPON Architecture Under Investigation

From the bottom (customer premises) to the top (CO), the model is as follows. The number of the CPEs and ONUs is equal to the total number of customers. The number of splitters is equal to the number of buildings. In the next level, the number of cabinets (Optical Mux/Demux) is estimated as:

$$\# \text{ of cabinets} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\# \text{ of splitters of the lower level}}{\text{splitting ratio of this level}} \right) \quad (23)$$

In the next two levels, the number of COs/OLTs is calculated from the required number of cabinets and the maximum number of cabinets per CO/OLT.

$$\# \text{ of COs/OLTs} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\# \text{ of cabinets}}{\text{max \# of COs/OLTs ports}} \right) \quad (24)$$

The required number of backplane ports of the CO/OLT is calculated through equation (25).

$$\# \text{ of CO/OLT backplane ports} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\# \text{ of xPON ports} * \text{xPON capacity}}{\text{backplane port capacity}} \right) \quad (25)$$

The number of required ports in the frontplane of CO/OLT is straightforward and is equal to the number of the backplane ports of the lower level's nodes. Thus, the total number of ports in each node corresponds to the sum of the frontplane and the backplane ports.

In the next step, one should calculate the required number of cards per capacity (26) as well as the required chassis (27) per node. Both are limited by the maximum number of ports per card and the maximum number of slots (for cards) per chassis, respectively.

$$\# \text{ of cards (capacity } i) = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\text{Node's ports (capacity } i)}{\# \text{ of ports per capacity } i \text{ card}} \right) \quad (26)$$

$$\# \text{ of chassis} = \text{ceil} \left(\frac{\sum \text{Node's capacity } i \text{ cards}}{\# \text{ of slots per chassis}} \right) \quad (27)$$

The total number of ports and cards as well as the total number of chassis in each level are estimated by multiplying the respective values per node with the number of nodes in each level. It should also be noted that the number of A/C and PSUs in each level is equal to the total number of nodes in each level.

The required number of the two sets of components, set1: BRAS, call server, call server software and RADIUS and set2: billing, IN/VAS and NMS, is calculated as in the case of VDSL.

6 XGain TE Analysis Framework

In this section the software design methodology, the design itself and the components that form the **XGain TE Analysis Framework** are presented.

6.1 Methodology

6.1.1 Design Methodology Goals

The design methodology aims to create a structured, modular Framework that can address the needs of the various technological and architectural models as well as the analysis methodology elements that will be exercised in the context of the project.

For the rest of this document the following terms will be used:

- The overall objective is to create a software **Framework**, where all the required analysis can be shaped and carried out. The Framework consists of documentation, data, procedures and means to modify and adapt the analysis supported, software (tools) and procedures to perform the analysis and use the results etc.
- At the core of the Framework resides the **Software**, which consists of several components that serve various purposes (e.g., analysis, data persistency, dimensioning, generic calculations etc) organised in modules (following the terminology where modules are bundles of components).
- On the other hand, the **Platform** is the technology behind the framework and its software and in operational context also other resources, such as hardware, network etc. behind the aforementioned framework.
- The **System** is a broader term and consists of software which operates on data, utilising configurations and using computational, storage and network and other resources to deliver results, which in cases also includes human handled processes and resources involved in the operation of the artefact.
- The “**Service**” is the view of the system as utilized by its clients, under the perspective that it is provided following *Software as a Service* paradigm, where the consumers of the system’s functionality interact with it via its exposed interfaces, not being concerned with the resources required for its operation or the maintenance of the software.
- **Arguments** are the inputs (either small values or larger data elements) that are passed to the System when performing an action, instructing it how to act in the particular occasion, while **configuration** stands for similar form inputs which are persisted by the System and not passed to it on a per action basis. Furthermore, the system may use **Data** that are associated to it by various means, in order to perform its actions.

Among the primary objectives of the design is to build a generic enough framework that can capture the analysis needs of various architectural, operation, business etc. models without requiring substantial rewrite of the software, but rather reorganising and extending it to capture only the gap among already provided models.

Yet, it is not the goal to implement a generic analysis engine that extends beyond the objectives of the techno-economic analysis of the project, thus assuming that a certain techno-economic analysis methodology elements

(as the ones presented in sections 3, 4 and 5 of this document) will become available (architecture, dimensioning, usage, costs, optional revenues, etc).

To address the goals presented a few key design points are settled:

- Shape the analysis process under a model that is generic enough to capture all known similar analysis processes.
- Shape system elements as components that each one serves a single purpose and may be interchangeable with others that may serve a similar purpose. Components of different classes will be defined to serve different purposes in the system, which will allow them to focus on particular operations and functionalities, rather than becoming unnecessarily too generic and unoriented.
- Avoid a platform and technological framework driven design to generalise for portability of the results.
- Adopt modern approach for interaction with external systems (REST API being the prominent modern approach for scalable, interoperable and maintainable services).

6.1.2 Implementation Methodology

The implementation methodology will follow the agile approach, mainly built around the concept of an implementation backlog that contains the items to be carried out, sprints that are small cycles of integrated design, development, small scale testing, and validation, and releases that are internal (i.e., not reaching general availability for analysis, but are suitable for larger scale validation) and external, which are targeting the analysts.

The process will be carried out by a team led by a product owner (that also validates the critical path and the overall strategy), a technical master (who can evaluate technical priorities and estimate size and impact of technical choices) and a compound work team that performs all the design, implementation and small-scale testing and validation commonly present at each sprint. The general agile approach will augment with the following elements:

- An upfront design will be presented, to encapsulate the overall objectives of the system. However, this design remains flexible to adapt according to the agile implementation process.
- The agile process will be followed with an adapted sprint timeline, where the duration of a sprint depends on the stage of the project, rather than a fixed sprint timeline. Sprints will vary from 1 to 4 weeks depending on the complexity and number of features that need to be combined at a particular stage of the project.
- The critical path of delivering essential software features for achieving project's objectives needs to be ensured by the sprints and releases, which means that specific tasks will be embedded in sprints as required in order for contractual objectives to be met at specific milestones of the project.

The implementation will be carried out using a modern framework (as presented in technology) and will be supported by a number of tools such as:

- Integrated Development environment suitable for the implementation platform.
- Code management platform for handling code (git).
- Ticketing system for managing backlog and software releases (Redmine).
- Build system for production of system packages (Apache Jenkins).

- Repository for delivery of the system packages (Docker Registry).

The aforementioned technologies will be utilised to facilitate implementation but are not built or configured as part of the project.

Regarding the verification of the software, the component-oriented design will be greatly supporting the unit test approach, however its application will be limited only to components that are mainly computational and easily separated from the surrounding system, in order to minimise need for mock implementation. Instead, integrated testing (i.e., components integrated and without mock-up implementations, acting on reference data) will be carried out, to drive end-to-end verification conclusions. Manual verification will be performed by users not involved in development, before software releases.

On the other hand, validation will be performed by the product owner, who will be continuously monitoring the alignment of the outcome with the objectives and needs of the project analysis.

6.1.3 Technology

For the implementation of the system the following technologies will be employed:

- Open Source Microsoft.Net core framework for the implementation of reusable software components.
- Open Source Microsoft.net core framework with WebAPI for implementation of the service that hosts the components of the system.
- Virtualisation based on docker Community Edition will be utilised for providing operational instances of the system.
- Open-Source PostgreSQL will be used for persistency of structured data.

6.2 Model and Architecture

6.2.1 XGain TE Analysis Platform Architecture

The logical architecture of the platform is depicted in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Analysis Framework Logical View

In the diagram we distinguish the following elements:

- The **Analysis Framework** is the virtual space where models are defined and analysed.
- An (analysis) **Client** is a process or tool that needs to perform an analysis of a model, providing its own inputs and data for this analysis. An example of a client is the KFT of XGain.
- The Client interacts with the platform via its Hyper-Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP) **API** component.
- Its **input and output data** are directed to (Analysis) Clients that need to perform an analysis via models hosted by the framework and correspond to model supplementary data as well as arguments for the execution of the model. Those are not generic but rather model-specific elements. Examples of such input data would be the dimensioning of a model that does not handle a specific architecture, the periods to run the model etc. Examples of output data would be IRR, IPV, Cash flows timeseries etc. The model is aware of what inputs it consumes and what outputs it produces.
- **Definitions of models**, are scripted in an imperative manner, however the Framework does not provide a user facing tool for authoring those models, and simple text editors may be utilised to form the model. A model is a list of calculators to be invoked at predefined stages of an analysis process, but in the future could also include additional and custom logic components.
- The **Compute components** are the containers of calculations and may be provided by the platform or be supplied alongside the definition of a model in an executable form. Depending on their targeted

invocation stage, those may be further distinguished semantically into various categories, such as pre-compute, post-compute, indicators, model facets etc, however they are structurally identical. Compute components may be grouped in modules that support a specific Analysis Engine; however, this is not mandatory and an Analysis Engine can be a completely autonomous module.

- An **Analysis Component** is the component of the platform that performs the analysis. It translates the model definition into a series of invocations ordered and repeated as intended by the model author, instantiates the components as needed and passes to them data that they need to perform their tasks, while steers their outputs to their target. Model analysis and Meta-analysis are two types of engines to be implemented.
- The **Model Compute Platform** is the orchestrator of the entire analysis process and instantiates components as needed, delegating to them the actual analysis tasks, while it interfaces with supporting components and services.
- The **Model Data Manager** is the persistency component of the platform and allows serialisation and deserialisation of models and data that may be deposited alongside them.
- The **Analysis Toolkit** is a summary of libraries that perform standard calculations that may be reused by all other components of the platform (e.g., IRR calculation, NPV and other formulas).
- The **DB Component** is responsible for fetching values for use by the models from configured external sources. It follows a specific API and may obtain those values also from its internal source. The engine has the ability to support several types of data items via extensibility modules. Initially it supports cost components along with their operational characteristics and pricing information.

6.2.2 Models

The fundamental element around which the rest of the Framework is built, is the Analysis Model. The primary aim of the platform is to be able to carry out the operations described by an Analysis Model.

An Analysis Model consists of a definition which dictates how the system will carry out the analysis and optionally a number of components (organised in one or more modules) to support this operation, if the components are not already part of another module or the platform itself.

It must be clarified though that an Analysis Model defines the process of analysis, and it is not a model of a specific case to be analysed (in contrast named as “Analysis Case Model”). The latter is formed by supplying adequate (according to the Analysis Model expectations) data to define the specific case. The platform does not tackle with the persistency of analysis case models, as this would require substantial additional technology which is partially available already in the case modelling tools that invoke the Analysis Framework.

Analysis Models are executed by proper Analysis Components. One of those Analysis Components is the XGain Model Analysis Engine.

The **XGain Model Analysis Engine** performs series of iterations of model calculations over a series of periods that form the study period of the model. Figure 15 contains a logical view of the Analysis Model, as carried out by the specific XGain Model Analysis Engine provided alongside the Framework.

Figure 15: Analysis Model Logical View

In this diagram we distinguish the following elements:

- **Analysis Model Definition** contains the instructions for the Engine on how to shape calculations and route inputs and outputs.
- **Input Data** include both configuration and arguments required to execute the model, as expected by both the engine and the model's components.
- **Pre-calculation components** are components that are executed on model input and other pre-calculation data and definition before the actual iterations of the model start. They are provided in an orderly fashion. Example of such components would be a dimensioning component.
- **Model iteration components** are components that are executed once per iteration of study periods. Such components could be period operation costs, period revenues etc.
- **Post-calculation components** are components that are executed on model input and interim data and definition after the actual iterations of the model end. They are provided in an orderly fashion. Examples of such components are indicator calculators (e.g. IRR).
- **Output Data** include results of the analysis, such as indicators and timeseries.
- **Analysis Iterator** which is the integral element of the XGain Model Analysis Engine that executes the iterations.

The XGain Model Analysis Engine is only one of the two Analysis Components implemented in XGain. The second analysis engine is the **XGain Meta-Analysis Engine**. It operates on top of models provided by XGain Model

Analysis Engine. It manipulates those models according to the definition of the Meta-analysis Model, executes them and gathers results from their execution.

Figure 16 contains a logical view of the Meta-Analysis Model, as carried out by the specific XGain Meta-Analysis Engine provided alongside the Framework.

Figure 16: Meta-analysis Model Logical View

In this diagram we distinguish the following elements:

- **Meta-Analysis Model Definition** contains the instructions for the Engine on how to shape calculations and route inputs and outputs.
- **Input Data** include both configuration and arguments required to execute the model, as expected by both the engine and the model's components.
- **Pre-calculation components** are components that are executed before the actual execution of the model(s) start. They are provided in an orderly fashion. Sensitivity analysis inputs adjustment is an example of such a component.
- **Pre-iteration components** are executed before the iterator engine starts invoking models (on each iteration).
- **Analysis models** are models as defined in previous text that are executed once per iteration of analysis steps.

- **Post-iteration components** are executed after the iterator engine finishes invoking models (on each iteration).
- **Post-calculation components** are components that are executed on model after the actual execution of the model finishes. They are executed after the iterator engine finishes. They are provided in an orderly fashion. Examples of such components are indicator calculators (e.g. delta cash flows if comparison of models is performed, sensitivity analysis data).
- **Output Data** include results of the analysis, such as indicators and timeseries.
- **Meta Analysis Iterator** which is the integral element of the XGain Meta Analysis Engine that executes the iterations of models. Internally it instantiates the XGain Model Analysis Engine to execute the models it needs to analyse.

The components to be implemented in XGain for Meta Analysis Engine will cover the need for **Sensitivity Analysis**.

6.3 Components

In the following paragraphs the components designed to be implemented during XGain are presented. The list of components, which are organised in modules that may be composing independent subsystems, shall not be considered final as the evolution of the design and componentisation is part of the Agile methodology followed by the project.

6.3.1 Model Data Manager

The component manages the definition of an Analysis Model or a Meta Analysis Model. To serve its persistency purpose, the component utilises a non-relational store. In its primary implementation it does not serve model cataloguing and search, and this is left to the Client to seek and use the proper model for an operation.

The component implementation allows the engine to handle two types of model definitions:

- **Analysis Models:** Host data regarding the execution of one model and its enclosure in pre/post calculation processes.
- **Meta Analysis Models:** Host data regarding the execution of one or multiple models as well as their enclosure in pre/post calculation processes.

Additionally, the components offer alongside the model areas to hold:

- Immutable arguments and input data provided to the Analysis Engine.
- Interim data (optionally).
- Output data.

Nevertheless, the internal structure of the component allows it to be expandable to handle other types of models, as long as a representation for the model is given and an Analysis component capable of consuming model's elements is in place.

Analysis Model data (accessed through the **Analysis Model Data Component**) contain the following elements, depending on the stage of the model:

- Model definition (Key= model id).
 - Model script definition.
 - Model descriptive metadata.
 - Model static configuration.
- Model instance data (Key= instance id, ref=model id).
 - Instance arguments / input data.
 - Instance descriptive metadata.
 - Instance Iteration Data on per period basis (key= instance id, period) (containing also Interim data).
 - Interim data (on period, by class, by id, reference to other entities).
 - Output data (on period, by class, by id, reference to other entities).
 - Designated data such as:
 - Assets (on period, by class, by asset, quantity, value).
 - Revenues (on period, by class, by revenue id, reference to other entities).
 - Costs (on period, by class, by cost id, reference to other entities).
 - Instance global data.
 - Interim data (by class, by id, reference to other entities).
 - Output data (by class, by id, reference to other entities).

Meta-analysis Model data (accessed through the **Meta-Analysis Model Data Component**) contain the following elements:

- Model definition (Key= model id).
 - Model script definition.
 - Model descriptive metadata.
 - Model static configuration.
- Model instance data (Key= instance id, ref=model id).
 - Instance arguments / input data.
 - Instance descriptive metadata.
 - Model data (Key = instance id, analysis model id, iteration no) (containing also Interim data).
 - Contains a full Analysis Model per model engaged, per iteration.
 - Iteration data (key = instance id, iteration no) (containing also Interim data).
 - Contains interim / summary data per iteration across models.
 - Instance global data (across models and iterations).
 - Interim data (by class, by id, reference to other entities).
 - Output data (by class, by id, reference to other entities).

It has to be noted that interim data shall be held by respective components in internal memory primarily. The model persistency area provisioning for interim data is an optional feature to be further considered in future implementations that would allow enhanced scalability under particularly heavy scenarios, in case those arise in the context of XGain.

6.3.2 Model Compute Component

The Model Compute component (a) loads the Model via Model Data Manager component, (b) loads the required modules that hold components required for the model execution, (c) runs those components' invocations as dictated by model's definition, (d) invokes any toolkit component required by model components and (e) persists the data via the support of the Model Data Manager, as dictated by the components.

- Handles model instantiation.
- Manages the Data Components of the model passing those to Computation Components and back and forth to the Model Data Manager. Passes dependencies to components according to the Dependency Injection design pattern.
- Instantiates and invokes the Analysis Engine to perform the iterations of the tasks.
- Invokes calculations as required by the Analysis Engine:
 - Pre calculations.
 - Periodic calculations.
 - Post calculations.
 - Meta analysis calculations.
- Invokes Toolkit Components as required:
 - Data access API.
 - Logging component.
- Supports error handling, logging and exceptions in a unified manner.

Model Compute exploits asynchronous programming for its internal tasks, however it does not offer multi-threaded model analysis, as this would put extra complexity in model definitions and the engine. More than one instance though can be run in different processes allowing the exploitation of additional resources, if present.

6.3.3 Analysis Engines

As already presented, the system will be provided with two Analysis Engines:

- XGain TE Model Analysis Engine.
- XGain TE Meta-analysis Engine.

Those two engines are implemented as two different components.

6.3.4 API

The model API is a component that allows the clients to interact with the Analysis Framework core via an HTTP API. It is offered as a REST API, however not the entire formalism of the paradigm will be followed in the context of XGain, due to time and complexity constraints. The API will be authenticated and clients will be able to invoke it via an access token that will be manually issued and registered in persistent storage. Future implementation may address this in an automated manner, or in conjunction with an Authentication and Authorisation infrastructure, however in the context of XGain it is found that no further security is required, beyond safeguarding the use of resources and the exposure of data.

6.3.5 Analysis Toolkit

The Toolkit hosts components that support the operation of the model and its modules. These, among others, include:

- Built-in calculators of the framework, as required by the Analysis Processes, in order to reduce the need for developing new components and modules for commonly applied formulas.
- Data components, to allow access to model data as well as common model elements (such as cost components, services etc.). Other components can build on top of those to modify or expand their functionality.
- Logging support components to represent exceptions, messages, operation results etc.

6.3.6 DB Component

The DB Component is the connector to data sources that provide access to data for elements used inside a model. Examples of elements are commonly commodity services and network components. Although the DB Component may support any kind of element, in the context of XGain, network components (cost components) will be implemented. Those have properties that define their behaviour, role in an infrastructure, connectivity options (e.g. fan-in, fan-out), cost, cost evolution, depreciation terms, maintenance terms etc.

The DB Component will be configured to draw data either from its internal database or from an external database service, which conforms to a particular REST API specification (only GET verb on resource is relevant).

6.3.7 Compute Components

Compute Components perform the actual calculations of the module, without interacting one with the other, but rather by exchanging data with the Model Data Component, though the intervention of the Model Compute Component.

They are invoked via the Analysis Engines as dictated by the respective model definitions and semantically can be of several types, however not differentiating in form but rather in essence.

- Execute-once are operations that execute ones in the lifetime of an analysis process.
 - Pre-calculation components: Executed only once, before the Analysis Model periodic modules, such as global data fetching modules, or parameters' expansion.
 - Post- calculation components: Executed only once after the Analysis Model periodic modules, such as aggregate indicators calculations.
- Repeated execution:
 - Model iteration components: Periodic execution modules are executed at every period of the analysis period.
 - Pre iteration components: Execute before the execution of an entire model, when repeated model executions are carried out by Meta-Analysis Iterator.

The following are a few components that will be implemented in XGain, according to the methodology:

- Model Cost Component Compute.

- Network Operation Cost Compute.
- Cash flow Compute.
- IRR Compute.
- NPV Compute.
- Sensitivity Analysis model parameter iterator.

6.4 Deployment and Operation

The deployment and operation of the XGain Analysis Framework makes use of virtualisation technology capable of scaling to fit the processing requirements that may arise, in alignment with the best practices for scalable elastic cloud services. Figure 17 depicts the deployment of XGain modules.

Figure 17: XGain Modules Deployment Diagram

- **Proxy Instance:** Hosts a reverse HTTP Proxy that receives requests to the engine. The Proxy directs the requests to any **Compute Instance** available. Although one instance is adequate for more cases, more than one proxies may be present, providing fault tolerance at proxy level.
- **Compute Instance:** Hosts all the modules (containing components) that can perform the analysis and accompany the framework. Many instances may be present or emerge as more load for processing arrives. The instances can cease to exist after they carry out the analysis task they perform, as the results are persisted outside their storage space. As the virtualisation technology permits it, a layer of

orchestration for the automated provisioning of new instances may be employed (e.g. Kubernetes), however this is not considered essential for the processing requirements of the XGain Project.

- **DB Instance:** Hosts the database server that handles data for elements used in the analysis, such as component characteristics, costs etc. Depending on the technology of the database server and the high availability model adopted, more than one instance may be present, however this is not required for the XGain Project needs.
- **Virtual Storage:** Hosts non-relational data managed and required by the models, such as model state, outputs, interim results etc. The storage is abstracted with an object-store API and in its simplest form is a shared file system mounted across all compute nodes such as NFS (Network File System).

For the needs of XGain the following infrastructure is employed:

- 4 Virtual Instances.
- 16 Virtual Cores (occasionally 32).
- 32GB RAM (occasionally 64).
- 100GB Persistent Storage.

7 Conclusions

In this first version of the deliverable “Techno-economic assessment of last-mile and edge technological solutions” due M12, the techno-economic methodology that will be used to assess all available last mile solutions at farm, community, and regional level was described. The inputs and the outputs (NPV, IRR, payback period etc.) of the techno-economic model are presented and analysed. The different components (demand, price evolution, maintenance etc.) were described in detail and form the target of the software to be released. The dimensioning rules of fixed networks are also provided.

The methodology for the development of the components of the techno-economic module is presented in abstract form and sketches its capability to cover the needs of the theoretical methodology. Although certain lines are drawn to limit the implementation to the targets of the project, the platform potentially has the capability to cover other analysis needs that may emerge in the course of the research performed.

The tools are designed with state-of-the-art concepts in mind and an outlook of provisioning under modern cloud computing approaches (as a service, scalable, portable etc).

The second version of the deliverable, due M25, will provide updates on the design of the Framework, following the Agile methodology presented and results from the application of the described methodology and tools on the assessment of the different scenarios/business cases.

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